

A POKA YOKE MECHANISM, AS A CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT ACTION IN A MANUFACTURING PROCESS

Author(s)*: Ion Cosmin GHERGHEA ¹, Constantin BUNGĂU ², Dan Claudiu NEGRĂU ³, Monica FAUR ⁴
Position: PhD Student¹, Prof., PhD², PhD Student³, PhD Student⁴
University: University of Oradea^{1,2}
Address: Oradea, Universităţii Str., No. 1, Romania ^{1,2,3,4}
Email: cosmin.gherghea@csud.uoradea.ro¹, bungau@uoradea.ro², dan.negrau@yahoo.com³,
monifaur@gmail.com⁴
Webpage: <https://www.uoradea.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – the paper presents a solution to eliminating waste, following some issues identified in the manufacturing process. The solution consists in a Poka yoke (mistake proofing) mechanism, which is a specific Lean manufacturing tool.

Methodology/approach - the research methodology includes a literature review on the application of poka yoke mechanisms in different operational processes, followed by a case study in which the main errors are identified. After identifying those problems in the manufacturing process, a poka yoke mechanism is designed, with the outcome of preventing those errors in the future operational process.

Findings – The proposed solution contributes to the safety during product operation, due to the assigned protection function, the reduction of operational and non-operational times, product quality increase, elimination of costs and profit increase.

Research limitations/implications – the study focuses on identifying an optimal solution to eliminate human errors. This adopted solution has contributed not only to the elimination of human errors in the manufacturing process, but also to the reduction of operational times, product quality increase and the enhanced safety at work.

Practical implications – The provided solution is meant to help the company to eliminate human errors, while increasing its production capacity.

Originality/value – The paper represents a part of the authors' research project, with the scope of developing a methodology for continuous improvement in the manufacturing process, by integrating poka yoke mechanisms in manufacturing on CNC machining centers.

Key words: poka yoke, Lean manufacturing, waste.

Introduction

Manufacturing is a complex process, in which new challenges often arise and the involved human factor must find the best solution, in the shortest possible time, at the lowest possible costs and gaining long-term benefits. Even if the design process and production planning are carefully conducted, and potential interruptions / failures are considered, they will appear sooner or later, either in a lower or a higher frequency.

Lean manufacturing is a concept developed by Toyota and its fundamental goal is to eliminate waste through continuous improvement. For this purpose, different Lean manufacturing techniques and methods of continuous improvement are used. (Faur and Bungau 2019), (Faur and Bungau 2018).

The aim of Lean production is to increase production efficiency by identifying and eliminating waste (Bungau et al 2012), (Bungau et al 2014), (Gherghea et al 2019). Often, these losses occur due to human error. To avoid and eliminate these errors, a mechanism called Poka yoke has been developed within Lean manufacturing (Pascal 2015). This mechanism is often designed in the production process to prevent or detect errors, and once these errors are identified, the process is stopped in order to fix the identified error (Sundar et al 2014).

This concept was invented by Shigeo Shingo in the mid-1960s, who was invited to Toyota by Taichi Ohno, the founder of the Toyota Production System (Rajan et al, 2016).

In the literature, poka yoke has several names, such as: foolproof systems (Anholon and Sano 2016), mistake proofing (Bhaskaran 2012), error proofing (Gupta and Kundra 2012), fool proof (Masai et al 2015), false proofing (Sundar et al 2014).

Poka yoke is a mechanism that prevents the occurrence of human errors in the manufacturing process, thus avoiding the occurrence of various types of losses, according to those identified in Lean production (Choomlucksana et al 2015). Also poka yoke can be applied to any type of process. According to Gherghea and Bungau (2018), the main waste caused by human errors are defects, ergonomic working conditions and unnecessary movements (Gherghea and Bungau 2018).

There is a strong link between the poka yoke mechanism and six sigma, because by implementing a poka yoke mechanism in a process, the defects are reduced, which leads to the process improvement, according to one of the benefits of the six sigma system (Singh 2019).

According to Rajan et al (2016), poka yoke is a mechanism that is part of the quality management system, being considered the most important TQM tool, significantly contributing to the process of continuous improvement within a Lean organization (Rajan et al 2016).

In the same paper the author presents the poka yoke mechanism (along with other TQM tools - Total Quality Management such as: Kaizen, 6 Sigma, JIT, jidco, FMS, etc.) as an important component in terms of developing a culture of quality within a company (Rajan et al, 2016).

Three types of poka yoke mechanisms have been identified: shutdown poka yoke, control poka yoke and warning poka yoke (Rajan et al, 2016).

The construction of such a mechanism within operational processes has significantly contributed to increasing product quality, eliminating waste, reducing operational and non-operational times, reducing costs and increasing customer satisfaction (Gherghea and Bungau 2018).

In any operational activity performed by a human operator, at some point an error may occur, due to several factors that may influence the activity of the operator. These errors can occur due to the lack of experience of the operator, unfavorable working conditions (dirt, unfavorable ergonomic position), insufficient information, insufficient preparation and training of the operator, fatigue, high stress etc (Li et al. 2016), (Cirjaliu and Draghici 2016).

In order to prevent and reduce these types of human errors, the careful analysis of the product is considered, but also the process in which the developed product is involved, taking measures (from the design phase) to prevent possible human errors (Wasim et al. 2013). After the main possible errors are identified, the poka yoke mechanism is designed to prevent the occurrence of those errors (Gherghea and Bungau 2018).

Research problem

The purpose of this paper is to present a practical solution that will eliminate a human error in an operational process. Following the identification of the problem, a poka yoke mechanism was developed, which eliminated this human error.

Therefore, in the case study, a poka yoke plate was designed (according to figure 1) on which the piece is placed, which has the role of simultaneously cutting the two radii of the cast piece (according to figure 2). At the same time, the role of the poka yoke plate is to position the cut piece in the correct cutting position, according to figure 3.

Before this device was designed, the part was cut by hand by the operators, which led to the appearance of scrap caused by improper cutting (due to human error).

The introduction of the poka yoke mechanism has significantly contributed to improving the operational process.

Figure 1. Poka yoke plate

Figure 2. Casting, simultaneous cutting of the two rays

Figure 3. Poka yoke plate

Research methodology

The research methodology is based on the analysis of the literature on the poka yoke mechanism, followed by case study where a poka yoke mechanism is implemented to avoid human errors, and in the same time having significant contribution to the elimination of other waste.

Discussion and conclusions

Following the identification of the problem, the cutting fixture rounds device was built, according to figure 2. The cut is made by the 2 profiled knives, heat treated, being made of C120 material (tool steel), designed and manufactured according to the two radii. With the design and implementation of the poka yoke mechanism, human error was eliminated, but it also had a significant impact on operational times, production cost and product quality (radius cutting quality), because due to the poka yoke mechanism the positioning of the part is much faster and also prevents incorrect positioning of the part.

The required time to manually cut for both rays was 45 seconds, and using the poka yoke mechanism is 5 seconds, which represents an increase in productivity by 88.88%. Considering 7.5 hours of work per day, the production capacity using the poka yoke mechanism is 5400 pieces processed per day, while for their manual processing, the production capacity is 600 pieces per day.

Also, the number of workers and cutting tools was reduced, from 2 workers to 1, and the risk of injuries due to manual cutting and the ergonomic position of the worker decreased.

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References

Anholon, R., and A. T. Sano

2016

“Analysis of Critical Processes in the Implementation of Lean Manufacturing Projects Using Project Management Guidelines.” *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 84(9–12): 2247–2256.

Bhaskaran, E.

2012

“Lean Manufacturing Auto Cluster at Chennai.” 93(December): 383–390.

Bungau, C, F. Blaga, and C. Gherghea

2014

“Kaizen Implementation for Cost Reduction in Manufacturing Process Product " Driver Control Board ".” 2014 International Conference on Production Research – Africa, Europe and Middle East 3rd International Conference on Quality and Innovation in Engineering and Management (QIEM): 55–58.

Bungau, C., F. Blaga and C. Gherghea

2012

“Continuous Improvement of Processes in Cutting Operations.” : 208–216.

Choomlucksana J., O. Monsiri and S. Phrompong

2015

“Improving the Productivity of Sheet Metal Stamping Subassembly Area Using the Application of Lean Manufacturing Principles.” *Procedia Manufacturing* 2(February): 102–107.

Cirjaliu, B. and A. Draghici

2016

“Ergonomic Issues in Lean Manufacturing.” *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 221: 105–110.

Pascal D.

2015

“Lean Productin Simplified” - A Plain - Language Guide to the World’s Most Powerful Production System. Third Edit. CRC Press.

Faur, M. and C. Bungau

2019

“Outsourcing Towards Greater Agility Through Investigating Decoupling Points in Leagile Supply Chains.” *MATEC Web of Conferences* 290: 1–13.

Faur M. and C. Bungau

2018

“Supply Chain 'Leagility' through Adopting Consignment Stock Strategy in Manufacturing Companies“, *Proceedings of the 6th RMEE Int. Mng. Conf. (Cluj- Napoca)* 623-632

Gherghea, I. C. and C. Bungau

2018

“Poka Yoke Application Synthesis in Manufacturing Engineering.” *Proceedings of the 6th Review of Management and Economic Engineering International Management Conference* 6: 564–571.

Gherghea, I. C., C. Bungau and D. C. Negrau

2019

“Best Practices to Increase Manufacturing Productivity - Comparative Study.” *MATEC Web of Conferences* 290: 1–9.

Gupta, A. and T. K. Kundra

2012

“A Review of Designing Machine Tool for Leanness.” *Sadhana - Academy Proceedings in Engineering Sciences* 37(2): 241–259.

Li, X., H. Zhao, X. Zhao and H. Ding

2016

“Dual Sliding Mode Contouring Control with High Accuracy Contour Error Estimation for Five-Axis CNC Machine Tools.” *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 108: 74–82.

Masai, P., P. Pierre and Z-M Cecilia

2015

"Towards a Formal Model of the Lean Enterprise." *Procedia - Procedia Computer Science* 60: 226–235.

Rajan K, R.K. Dwivedi and V. Ajay

2016

Indian Journal of Engineering. *Indian Journal of Engineering*, 13(33), 362–370.

Singh, Y. and K. T. Rupinder

2019

"Process Improvement by Poka-Yoke : A Tool for Zero Defects Process Improvement by Poka-Yoke : A Tool for Zero Defects." 9(July): 152–156.

Sundar, R., A. N. Balaji, and R. M. Satheesh Kumar

2014

"A Review on Lean Manufacturing Implementation Techniques." *Procedia Engineering* 97: 1875–1885.

Wasim, Ahmad, E. Shehab, H. Abdalla, A. Al-Ashaab, R. Sulowski and R. Alam

2013

"An Innovative Cost Modelling System to Support Lean Product and Process Development." *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 65(1–4): 165–181.